

Effect of damping ratio and hardening on the Dynamic Increase Factor for a column loss hazard

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ABSTRACT

Accidental actions like bomb blasts, gas explosions or car collisions are severe hazards that can pose a structure to extreme demands and potentially lead to collapse. To cope with these actions and avoid undesirable failures, indirect or direct design methods could be implemented. The alternate path method (ALP) has been a particularly popular direct design method among designers and researchers as it can efficiently study the capability of a structure to redistribute the loads under a column loss scenario in a computer-based environment. The application of this method is mostly efficient with static analyses rather than dynamic due to the smaller degree of modelling and analysis complexities associated with them; however, their use would necessitate the consideration of a Dynamic Increase Factor (DIF). Traditional standards such as the Unified Facility Criteria (UFC) for progressive collapse of buildings, propose DIFs that are based on ductility. The effect of other important parameters such as hardening or damping ratio is not explicitly captured by these provisions. This paper aims to highlight the distinct effect of these parameters and compare it with the UFC provisions and other recommendations in the literature. For this purpose, an analytical methodology based on a nonlinear SDOF system which accounts for these factors is used for the estimation of the DIFs. The results presented in this work demonstrate the important effect of both damping ratio and hardening on the DIF and how different predictive models compare to each other depending on the size these factors attain.

Keywords: Progressive collapse, Column loss, Dynamic Increase Factor, Damping ratio, Hardening, Alternate Load Path.

1 INTRODUCTION

Progressive collapse risk is a major design concern for buildings especially for those with a high importance level. Recent catastrophic incidents such as the Tower Centres in 2011 or the Murrah building in 1995 has proven the tragic consequences such a failure is associated with. Many research efforts have therefore been made in the last decades to study the phenomenon and address it. Nowadays, this special hazard type is covered extensively by design codes such as GSA (1), FEMA (2), DoD (3) and EC1-7 (4).

Collapse of buildings is typically caused by a sudden loss of critical components. Among these, the loss of a column is associated with the highest risk due to the significant extra demand it can impose to neighbouring elements. Among the design methods proposed for this hazard, the Alternate Path Method (APM) is the most widely used method. Based on this method, once a column is removed from a structure, the building should be able to provide to the gravity loads an alternate load path. The greatest advantage of the method is that it is a structural analysis model-based method meaning that the design against the hazard can be based on 3D finite element models similarly to those typically used for the design against normal loads. The analysis type could vary from a static analysis to a fully nonlinear dynamic analysis. In the latter case the dynamic response

could be estimated with high accuracy however, the complexities in the modelling, time for analysis and expertise from behalf of the analyst is significant. Methods involving a static analysis on the other hand are easier to cope with, however they necessitate the use of a DIF to account for the amplification in the response associated with the abrupt removal of the column.

In the literature, one could identify two different methods for the derivation of DIF formulations. According to the first method which is based on simplified nonlinear SDOF systems, analytical equations are produced while in the second case, the formulas are empirically produced by a regression analysis of a data set produced from extensive numerical analyses. For example, Tsai and Lin (5) proposed an analytical method for the DIF, based on the pseudo-static response of a bilinear elastic plastic SDOF model where the produced DIF was related to the post-elastic stiffness ratio and the ductility demand. Mashhadi et al. performed two separate parametric analyses to investigate the effect on the progressive collapse response of multi storey buildings firstly of the damping ratio ξ in (6) and secondly of hardening h in (7) and provided two formulas based on the equation adopted by the UFC recommendations to account for their effects independently one to the other. The DIF formula which was adopted by UFC (8) was the outcome of a research made by McKay et al. in 2012 (9). Earlier, in 2008, Stevens et al. (10) derived a different DIF expression for steel structures. More recently, Dimopoulos (11) proposed an analytical methodology for the estimation of DIF that took into account besides the post-elastic stiffness ratio and ductility demand, also the damping ratio which distinguishes it from the proposal of Tsai and Lin (5).

In the literature, one could identify two types of DIFs, a force-based and a displacement-based. While the first is used to increase the applied loads in a static analysis to account for the amplified displacement demands of the dynamic event, the latter could be used in a linear analysis to increase the rotation demands. The aim of this research is to evaluate the effect of the damping and hardening ratios on the force-based DIF using the methodology proposed in (9) and compare its predictiveness with the aforementioned recommendations found in the literature. For this purpose, the proposed method for the estimation of the force-based DIF, named as DIF_f thereafter, is presented first, followed by other relevant recommendations. Selected verification results of the model using a nonlinear finite element model in OpenSees are then provided. Then, the effect of ξ and h on the DIF_f is demonstrated using the analytical model and a comparison among different DIF proposed formulas is then made. Finally, key conclusions are given at the end.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Governing equations

The newly developed DIF_f is based on an analytical methodology which uses a nonlinear SDOF system to simulate the loss of a critical column and estimates the dynamic response in the time domain. The analytical model takes into account the elastoplastic properties of the hardened system in accordance with equation (1) and damping. To imitate the sudden column loss, a time step function is used. The hardened model is characterized with an initial K_1 and a hardened K_2 stiffness, hardening ratio $h = k_2/k_1$, a yield force F_y and displacement u_y and a mass m . For the solution of the problem, it is required to consider the three different stages of motion that characterize an elastoplastic system: namely (1) the elastic stage, (2) the inelastic stage and (3) the rebound stage. The system would reach a peak displacement u_i^* ($= u_{i,max}$), where $i=1$ if the system remains elastic and $i=2$ if the system behaves plastically. The peak displacements in this paper were extracted from the displacement time history responses.

$$F_s(u) = \begin{cases} ku, & u \leq u_y \\ F_y + k_p(u - u_y), & u_y \leq u \leq u_2^* \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The produced governing equations for each stage are given in equations (3)-(5):

$$\text{Stage I: } m\ddot{u} + 2m\omega_1\xi\dot{u} + k_1u = P_{0,1} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Stage II: } m\ddot{u} + 2m\omega_2\xi\dot{u} + k_2u = P_{0,2} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Stage III: } m\ddot{u} + 2m\omega_1\xi\dot{u} + k_1u = P_{0,3} \quad (4)$$

The effective applied force $P_{0,i}$, in these expressions, depends on the motion stage and assumes the expressions of equation (6). u_2^* in this equation but also in (1), corresponds to the peak displacement reached by the system in stage 2.

$$P_{0i} = \begin{cases} P_0, & \text{Stage I (i = 1)} \\ P_0 - F_y + k_2u_y, & \text{Stage II (i = 2)} \\ P_0 - F_y - k_2u_2^* + k_2u_y + k_1u_2^*, & \text{Stage III (i = 3)} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1. Properties of the SDOF system (a) mechanical model, (b) free body diagram, (c) force-displacement function and (d) load function.

The solution for the displacement and velocity of the system is given by equation (6) and (7), respectively, where A_i and B_i are constant parameters depending on the initial conditions and the effective load.

$$u_i(t) = \frac{P_{0,i}}{k_i} + e^{-\xi\omega_i t} (A_i \cos(\omega_{di}t) + B_i \sin(\omega_{di}t)) \quad (6)$$

$$\dot{u}_i(t) = e^{-\xi\omega_i t} ((B_i\omega_{di} - A_i\omega_i\xi)\cos(\omega_{di}t) - (A_i\omega_{di} + B_i\omega_i\xi)\sin(\omega_{di}t)) \quad (7)$$

$$\omega_{di} = \omega_i\sqrt{1 - \xi^2} \quad (\text{for } i=1-3) \quad (8)$$

$$A_i = -\frac{(P_{0,i} - k_i u_{i,0})}{k_i} \quad \text{and} \quad B_i = \frac{\dot{u}_{i,0}}{\omega_{di}} - \frac{P_{0,i}\omega_i\xi}{k_i\omega_{di}} + \frac{\xi\omega_i u_{0,i}}{\omega_{di}} \quad (9)$$

2.2 Previously proposed Dynamic Increase Factors

Once the time history response of the displacement is obtained from equations (6) and (7), the peak displacement u^* can be estimated. Then, DIF_f which is defined as the ratio of the static force (P_{st}) to the dynamic force (P_{dyn}) under an equal displacement demand u^* can easily be obtained.

$$DIF_f = \frac{P_{st}}{P_{dyn}} = \begin{cases} \frac{ku^*}{P_0}, & u_1^* < u_y \\ \frac{F_y + k_p(u^* - u_y)}{P_0}, & u_1^* \geq u_y \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

2.3 Previously proposed Dynamic Increase Factors

Other DIF_f formulae proposed in the literature for consideration in static analyses as already presented in the introduction are given by the following equations where μ and m are defined as the ratio of the total displacement or the plastic replacement over the yield displacement, respectively:

- Tsai and Lin (5)

$$DIF_f = \frac{2\mu(1 + \alpha(\mu - 1))}{1 + \alpha(\mu - 1)^2 + 2(\mu - 1)} \quad (11)$$

- McKay et al. (9) and UFC (3)

$$DIF_f = 1.08 + \frac{0.76}{m + 0.83} \quad (12)$$

- Stevens et al. (10)

$$DIF_f = 1.44m^{-0.12} \quad (13)$$

- Mashhadi et al. (7)

$$DIF_f = (2 - 2.54\xi) - \frac{(0.9 - 1.81\xi)\theta_p/\theta_y}{(0.84 - 2.15\xi) + \theta_p/\theta_y} \quad (14)$$

- Mashhadi et al. (6)

$$DIF_f = (1.1 + 2\eta) + \frac{0.56 + \eta}{0.65 + \theta_p/\theta_y} \quad (15)$$

2.4 Numerical modelling of the SDOF system in OpenSees

The analytical equations were implemented in MATLAB (12) and their accuracy was verified using a simplified nonlinear SDOF model in OpenSees (13) as shown in *Fig. 2*. To account for the nonlinear properties of the system spring, a zero-length element with a ‘unialMaterial Steel01’ material was used. The mass of the system was attached at node 2, the top of the spring. The spring was fully fixed at the bottom and left free at the top to move only longitudinally. The applied load at node 2 was considered using a step function load. Mass proportional damping was considered via the Rayleigh damping command. Finally, the dynamic analysis was performed using the Newmark average acceleration method with 0.001sec as a time step.

Fig. 2. OpenSees model for the SDOF system.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Verification of analytical model

The response characteristics of a linearly elastic ($P_0/F_y = 0.5$) and an inelastic system ($P_0/F_y = 1.0$) for a damping ratio ξ of 0.10 are presented in Fig. 3. The accuracy of the analytical model is evident from the excellent agreement with the OpenSees results.

Fig. 3. Displacement time history plots of an elastic and an inelastic damped oscillator and two different load factors P_0/F_y ($= 0.5$ (a) and 1.0 (b)) ($h = 0.05, k = 20000 \text{ kN/m}, m = 30 \text{ kNm}^{-1} \text{sec}^2, P_0 = 250 \text{ kN}, F_y = 500 \text{ kN}$).

3.2 Effect of hardening and damping ratios

The effect of damping ratios on the DIF_f of the SDOF system under the action of a column removal is examined here. For this purpose, a parametric analysis was performed considering different values for ξ ($= 0.0 - 0.20$), load-strength P_0/F_y ($= 0.02 - 1000$) and hardening ratio h ($= 0.0, 0.10$). In Fig. 4, the variation of the DIF_f of an undamped SDOF system with respect to P_0/F_y and μ ratios for the examined h values is presented. The results indicate that for small P_0/F_y values (≤ 0.50), the DIF is equal to 2.0 as expected for elastic undamped systems. It can be seen that DIF_f attains the smallest value for P_0/F_y ratio equal to 1.0. For larger load ratios the DIF_f increases and converges to 2.0 for very large ductility values. As the hardening ratio increases, DIF_f increases indicating that the more elastic-like the systems are, the larger the DIF_f values are. Fig. 4 (b) and (c) show the deviation between the DIF_f of a hardened system compared to a system with a very small hardening ratio equal to 1.0% which was chosen as a reference case for comparison purposes. As an appreciation of the effect of hardening ratio on DIF, as the h changes from 1% to 5% (or to 20%), the DIF increases by 11% (or by 32%). On the other hand, the consideration of damping tends to increase the DIF for any load intensity and similarly the ratio of increment of DIF_f as h increases (Fig. 5).

In Fig. 6 the effect of damping ratio for the two hardening ratios (0.02 and 0.20) is provided with respect to P_0/F_y (a) and μ (b). The important effect of damping ratio on DIF_f is clear. Both elastic and inelastic systems at very large ductility demands, show the same effect of ξ on the DIF_f . For intermediate values of P_0/F_y (or ductility μ), the DIF_f is affected less from ξ for either of the two hardened ratios (2% and 10%) with the smallest impact (practically negligible for 2%) for P_0/F_y (or μ) equal to 1.0 (Fig. 7).

Fig. 4. DIF_f and normalized DIF_f as a function of P_0/F_y (a, c) and ductility μ (b, d) for an undamped system and different hardening ratios ($h=1.0\%$, 2% , 5% , 10% , 20%)

Fig. 5. DIF_f and normalized DIF_f as a function of P_0/F_y (a, c) and ductility μ (b, d) for a damped system with $\xi=0.10$ and different hardening ratios ($h=1.0\%$, 2% , 5% , 10% , 20%).

Fig. 5 (continued). DIF_f and normalized DIF_f as a function of P_0/F_y (a, c) and ductility μ (b, d) for a damped system with $\xi=0.10$ and different hardening ratios ($h=1.0\%$, 2% , 5% , 10% , 20%).

Fig. 6. DIF_f and normalized DIF_f as a function of P_0/F_y (a, c) and ductility μ (b, d) for a system with $h=0.02$ and different damping ratios ($\xi=0\%$, 5% , 10% , 15% , 20%)

Fig. 7. DIF_f and normalized DIF_f as a function of P_0/F_y (a, c) and ductility μ (b, d) for a system with $h=0.20$ and different damping ratios ($\xi=0\%$, 5% , 10% , 15% , 20%)

3.3 Comparison of alternative DIF formulae

In this section, the predictiveness of the five different DIF_f formulae and how they compare with each other is presented. Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 provide the DIF_f predictions of these formulas as a function of P_0/F_y (a) and ductility μ (b). From these results, some very interesting observations can be made. First of all, the new DIF_f formula provides the same predictions as those of Tsai & Lin when no damping is considered, however, only the new methodology can take into account the effect of damping. The model by Mashhadi et al (2016), provides close predictions to those of the new proposal for ductility values between 0 and 5, however, for $\mu=0$, DIF assumes a value of 2.0 (i.e. no damping is taken into account). Moreover, for larger μ , it convergences to a value close to 1.0 in contrast to the increased DIF values the newly proposed method (and that in (5)) estimates due to the hardening effect of the system. From the six models, three of them converge to DIF values close to 1.0 for very large μ values. A different behaviour is exhibited by the Stevens et al. formula which is a monotonically decreasing function that estimates DIF values even smaller than 1.0 for large μ values.

Fig. 8. DIF_f with respect to load ratio P_0/F_y (left column) and ductility μ (right column).

Fig. 9. DIF_f with respect to load ratio P_0/F_y (left column) and ductility μ (right column).

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This paper presented the effect of ξ and h on the DIF_f using an analytical methodology based on a nonlinear SDOF model and compared alternative formulae proposed for the prediction of DIF. It has been observed that the DIF_f assumes same values when the system behaves either elastically or exhibits extremely large ductility values based on two models (Dimopoulos and Tsai & Lin) while the rest either converge to 1.0 or they are monotonically decreasing. These two models provide the same results for undamped systems but only the former can take into account ξ . All the rest models provide similar results generally for small μ values when no damping is considered and for small (a few %) hardening ratios and they give 8-12% larger predictions compared with the aforementioned two cases. Current design recommendations either ignore the effect of damping and hardening ratios in the estimation of the DIF or they consider them in an empirical and incomplete manner. The presented results indicate that the proposed methodology could be a useful alternative method for a more reliable and system-related assessment against progressive collapse that could explicitly take into account these important mechanical parameters.

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